

Evaluation and Comparison of Retention in Mandibular Implant Supported Overdenture by Using Ball and Flat Attachment –an in Vitro Study

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this in vitro study was to compare the retention in mandibular implant supported overdenture by using ball and ball attachments. Edentulous mandibular models were made with heat-cured polymethyl methacrylate resin. Two implant replicas (CMI), of 3.75 mm diameter and 10 mm length, were placed in the intraforaminal region. Acrylic resin mandibular overdentures were fabricated and provision was made to receive two different overdenture attachment systems, prefabricated ball/o-ring attachment (Lifecare Biosystems, Thane, India) and Hader bar and clip attachment (Sterngold, Attleboro, MA). Using a universal testing machine. Statistical analysis comprised Shapiro-Wilk test, and student t test. The statistical model revealed a significantly different behavior of the attachment systems both before and between the ball/o-ring and bar attachments developed higher retentive force as compared to the locator attachment. The bar and clip attachment exhibited the highest peak as well as the highest mean retention force at the end of the study. The Locator® attachment showed a decrease in retentive potential after an early peak. The bar and clip attachment exhibited the greater mean retention force in comparison to ball/-o ring attachment.

KEY WORDS: dental implant, overdenture, ball attachment, flat attachment

INTRODUCTION:

The most common problem associated with the management of edentulous patients is the severely resorbed mandibular ridge, especially in older age when adaptive capacities are reduced^[1-3]. This compromised situation consequently results in the fabrication of unsatisfactory dentures with poor retention and stability which can further precipitate psychosocial problems^[4-5].

The stabilization of the lower denture with two interforaminal implants has provided reliable and predictable treatment outcomes. It is regarded as the minimum standard of care for edentulous patients^[6]. Implant-supported over dentures have been shown to provide a successful long-term outcome, particularly

when used to restore edentulous mandibles. It is stated that treatment effects in conjunction with a high implant success rate, improve in oral function and patient satisfaction. Various attachment types have been employed, usually ball attachment and flat attachment. Incorporating these attachments in a denture is less time consuming and low costs of components make their use cheaper when compared to bar-clip attachment.

The branemark system have been established for implant prostheses in the edentulous mandible:(1) implant – supported fixed prosthesis, (2) removable implant –supported overdenture and (3) combined implant –retained /soft tissue –supported overdenture prosthesis^[7].

The prognosis of the prosthesis depends on Retention. It is the function of and is directly related to the attachment system employed. The success of implant-retained overdentures primarily depends on the retentive capacity of its attachment element to sustain its long-term functionality^[8].

It is hypothesized that attachments, which provide more retention against vertical and horizontal dislodgement, will be more favourable to oral function, patient satisfaction and could be the choice

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of attachment type. To investigate this hypothesis, a study has been designed in which two attachment types are compared with respect to aspects of oral function. The purpose of this study is to evaluate and compare the retention in mandibular implant supported overdenture by using two different attachment systems.

The aim of study was to compare the retention in mandibular implant supported overdenture by using ball and flat attachments.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

The present study is an in vitro cross sectional study. The study was conducted in the Department of Prosthodontics of RKDF Dental College and Research Centre. The research had been approved by Institutional Ethical Committee of College.

Mandibular Overdentures were fabricated in a conventional manner using heat polymerized polymethyl methacrylate resin-(DPI Heat Cure, DPI, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India)

The implant analogs (CMI 3.75 mm × 10 mm) were placed in the acrylic models using physiodyspenser, simulating the conventional placement of implant in osteotomy site in the mandible and subsequently secured with resin cement (Relyx™, 3M ESPE, USA). Two overdenture models were prepared and eight denture samples were prepared for each group. The samples were divided in two groups based on the attachment:

Group A: Ball/o-ring attachment;

Group B: Bar and clip attachment.

Prefabricated ball attachment (Lifecare Bio-systems, Thane, India): A metallic housing with a rubber o-ring component was used for the ball and ring attachment.

Hader bar and clip attachment (Figure 1)

A castable Hader bar of length = 22 mm;

diameter = 1.8 mm = 13 gauge.

Nylon rider-length = 5 mm; width = 2.6 mm - moderate Retention

Figure 1: Showing hader bar and clip attachment.

Each attachment system was secured into the implant replicas on the acrylic resin model and the overdentures with the corresponding housing were subsequently placed on it and tightened to 35 Ncm.

Prosthetic phase:

After healing of soft tissue, Acrylic overdentures with respective attachment systems were placed on the acrylic edentulous mandibular models. Metallic clips were attached to the dentures and secured with clear autopolymerized acrylic resin (DPI Cold Cure, Clear, DPI, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India). The edentulous acrylic model was secured in place using a surveyor table.

Retention:

A universal testing machine (Model 5T, China Material Technological Co., Taipei, Taiwan) was applied to test retentive force for each experimental overdenture at a cross-head speed of 50 mm/min. This crosshead speed has been reported to approximate clinically relevant movement of the denture away from the edentulous ridge. A metallic chain connected the universal testing machine to the overdenture framework at the withdrawal loops. Vertical testing forces simulated anticipated overdenture removal forces 21 Peak load-to-dislodgement and strain-at-dislodgement were recorded and calculated from stress-strain curves in order to determine the retention force and the change of distance between the patrix and the matrix of each attachment system respectively^[9].

RESULTS:

The mean force to dislodge the mandibular overdenture in all the patients was 8.87 ± 2.04 N. In bar and clip attachment group was 10.72 ± 0.76 N while in the Ball attachment group was 7.02 ± 0.70 N (Table 1; Figure 2).

The test of normality was performed on data and the Shapiro-Wilk test shows the p value of 0.53 and 0.43 which means the data is normally distributed and parametric test can be applied to the data for comparing the data (Table 2).

The t Test was used to compare the differences in force used to dislodge the denture. The mean force used to dislodge the denture was 10.72 ± 0.76 N in the bar attachment group while the force required to dislodge the mandibular denture was 7.02 ± 0.70 N in the ball attachment group. The test results show there was statistically significant difference in the amount of force required to dislodge the denture. The amount of force required in the bar attachment was greater as compared to the ball attachment. The amount of retention is more in the bar attachment group as compared to the ball attachment group (Table 3).

Table 1: Description of amount of force required to dislodge mandibular overdenture among different kind of mandibular supported overdenture.

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Median	Range
Bar Attachment	8	10.72	.76	10.56	2.13
Ball Attachment	8	7.02	.70	7.12	1.93
Total	16	8.87	2.04	8.86	5.95

Figure 2: Description of amount of force required to dislodge mandibular overdenture among different kind of mandibular supported overdenture.

Table 2: Test for Normality for the data.

Groups	Shapiro -Wilk Test			
	Statistic	df	Sig.	
Force in Newton	Bar Attachment	.931	8	.528
	Ball Attachment	.920	8	.430

DISCUSSION:

The underlying principle in employing retentive implant-overdenture systems for the treatment of edentulous patients is to increase denture retention and stability, thereby promoting chewing function as well as patient comfort and compliance^[10,11].

Ball, and Bar attachments are the commonly used anchorage systems in implant-supported overdentures and their efficacy is scientifically supported^[11]. Hence, these attachment systems were chosen for this study. Splinted conventional bar attachments have demonstrated superior retentive capacities over unsplinted systems. However, they have a few disadvantages; they are initially more expensive, difficult to repair, and maintaining oral hygiene seems difficult, especially for fragile elderly individuals^[12,13].

In comparison with the bar attachments, ball anchors were preferred by clinicians because they were less technique sensitive, cost-effective, easy to use and to repair^[14].

Table 3: comparison in Amount of force required to dislodge mandibular overdenture

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t value	p value
Bar Attachment	8	10.72	.76	10.12	0.01 (S)
Ball Attachment	8	7.02	.70		

This study was performed under a controlled experimental simulation to evaluate the retentive forces of three different types of anchorage systems used for implant-supported overdentures. The experimental set-up, however, may have had a few limitations. The sample size of the specimen used was relatively small, but was in accordance with previous similar experiments^[13].

It has to be kept in mind that for the current *in vitro* experiment, only mono-directional forces were applied, which does not represent a realistic model for a clinical situation with overdentures. There, the main forces are generated in the region of the first molars which will lead to rotational forces on the attachments through leverage.

During the course of the study, the different attachments showed a complex evolution with peaks as well as increasing and/or decreasing mean retentive forces. The statistical model revealed a significantly different behavior of the attachment systems.

The bar and clip attachment exhibited the significantly higher mean retention force in comparison to ball attachment at the end of the study. The same result was obtained by Shastry T et al^[17], who find The bar and clip attachment exhibited the highest mean retention force in comparison to locator and ball attachment system but found any significant difference between groups.

CONCLUSION:

The bar and clip attachment exhibited the greater mean retention force in comparison to ball/-o ring attachment. The study recommended further *in vivo* research to understand the loss in retention force of various overdenture attachment systems.

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